

Milestone: MS17 - Second technical expert seminar held

Lead Participant: UU

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Due: June 2024

Date Of Completion: 11/10/2023

Means of Verification

Workshop in Rome, 9--11 October 2023.

Main themes were tutorial on the starter kit products, hack a node in shape, working towards MS7, user portal functionality, and data management.

Folder with agenda.

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

The work was done in autumn 2023. Slide finalised in June 2024.

Project participants & others

92 project members from 21 countries participated in the workshop, see folder above.

During the first workshop, we focused only on the starter kit. This time, we added another part of the work in pillar II, data management.

The meeting was facilitated by UU (WP5.1 leads and WP3 leads). The agenda was co-created by WP leads in pillar II.

Next action steps

The next step was primarily to prepare for milestone 7, which was submitted in April 2024.

